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APPLICATION OF RESOURCE EFFICIENT IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN BUKHARA REGION

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Annotation: *The article presents the results of research on drip irrigation. With the use of water-saving irrigation technology, the surface layer of the soil is not compacted or the volume weight is reduced compared to the traditional method, the water permeability of the soil is improved, mineral fertilizers are not washed away, as well as the marginal field moisture capacity of the soil. The results of the research on the fact that when cotton is irrigated in the 70-80-65% system, up to 53% of water is saved and the yield is 7.4-10.6 c/ha higher than the control. It was also observed that when irrigation was carried out by laying a black polyethylene film between the rows of cotton, the productivity increased by 9.7-20.4 c/h along with the saving of water resources, mineral fertilizers, and technical resources. During the growing season, when irrigation is carried out with the help of portable flexible pipes, up to 20.5% of water per hectare can be saved, irrigation works are simplified, and cotton growth and development are provided due to the short-term supply of water to the field. It was observed that it changed in a positive direction and the productivity increased by 3.0 c/h compared to the option when irrigated in the traditional way.*

Key words: *drip irrigation technique, technology, dropper, mineral fertilizer, yield, mineralization, cotton, efficiency, dropper, sprinkler, volume weight, polyethylene pipe, soil.*

Our government is paying serious attention to improving the culture of irrigation in our country, carrying out reforms in water management, strengthening the material and technical base of the sector, modernizing it, and desertification. Introduction of advanced methods of crop irrigation, including drip irrigation, irrigation by laying black polyethylene film on the ground, irrigation using portable flexible pipes, irrigation by introducing hydrogel crystal into the soil. Large-scale works are being put into practice. In particular, the Cabinet of Ministers "On measures to improve the reclamation of irrigated lands and rational use of water resources during 2020-2024" and "Introduction of drip irrigation system and new water-saving irrigation technologies and on measures for the effective organization of financing" have been adopted and activities are being implemented accordingly. The technology of caring for cotton in the drip irrigation system includes the following main indicators: the use of high-yielding and fast-ripening varieties suitable for different soil and climate conditions, a rational system of basic, pre-ploughing and inter-row cultivation of the soil, planting high-quality seeds, application of a system that fully automates the irrigation process, helps to use water efficiently and effectively, a combined protection system for plants from diseases, pests and weeds, defoliation and harvesting of cotton with the help of machines. The main difference of the drip irrigation system is that during the growing season, it is possible to introduce a certain amount of mineral fertilizers and herbicides to the plant along with the irrigation water, and the cotton is treated between the rows until the first water, and then then until the end of the growing season, there is absolutely no processing (cultivation) between the rows.

In order to introduce drip irrigation technology to perfect study and production on a scientific basis, scientific research work was carried out at the educational-scientific center of the "TIAME" NRU Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management. The soil of the experimental area is medium loam, the depth of groundwater is 2.2-2.5 meters, and during the period of cotton growth, it is 1.9-2.2 meters, less salty. According to the results of the experiment, the drip irrigation system has some advantages compared to the drip irrigation system, which saves 45-50% of the irrigation water, 40-50% of the fuel, lubricants and mineral fertilizers. Economy has been found in studies. Also, it was found that the number of inter-row processing is reduced by 6 times, and 85 cbm/ha of water is used to grow 1 c/ha of cotton.

We can observe that the water-physical properties of the soil have changed in a positive direction in the drip-irrigated "delyanka" compared to the field irrigated using the traditional

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method, including: reduction of volume weight, improvement of water permeability of the soil. It was found that productivity increased by 7.3-10.7 c/h during drip irrigation. In addition, due to constant moisture retention in the drip-irrigated area, the salinity process in the soil was observed very little, it was not affected by diseases and pests, especially wilt disease. The mechanical composition of the soil of the experimental areas is medium loam, the medium-fiber cotton variety Bukhara-10 was planted with a distance of 60 cm between rows. The volumetric weight of the soil in the driving layer of the soil (0-30 cm) is 1.38-1.41 g/cm³, and in the sub-driving layer (30-50 cm) this indicator is slightly increased to 1.49-1.58 g /cm³, specific gravity and total porosity were 3.14-3.21 g/cm³ and 51.3-47.1 % in these layers, respectively.

The water-physical properties of the soil are as follows: limited field moisture capacity (LFMC) in the 0-100 cm part of the soil layer is 20.3-21.4, natural moisture is 17.2-18.5% in the driving layer, and 18.3 in the sub-driving layer equal to -20.8%, the cotton irrigation procedure was formed based on the amount of pre-irrigation moisture determined in the experimental system and the calculated layer of soil 0-50 cm. The data obtained during the growing season indicate a higher efficiency of drip irrigation than irrigation through the egate. For example, 5,200 cbm/ha of gross water was consumed during the season in irrigation by egate, 2,280 cbm/ha in drip irrigation options 2 and 3, and 2,760 cbm/ha in the fourth option (70-80-65). we can observe that water has been used up. Thus, 53% of water was saved when using drip irrigation in the order of 70-75-70%, and 47% of water was saved when using drip irrigation in the order of 70-80-65%.

The characteristics of agrotechnics for the maintenance of cotton and crops belonging to its complex in the conditions of old irrigated meadow alluvial soils in drip irrigation systems are described above. In these experiments, the high efficiency obtained in terms of water saving has also shown its positive effect from an environmental point of view. Grassy alluvial soils are prevented from widespread irrigation erosion in the region and leaching of mineral fertilizers along with wastewater. Through this method, the root layer of the crop is constantly supplied with moisture and provides a good opportunity to absorb water and nutrients. The advantage of drip irrigation is, first of all, in saving water resources. This is achieved due to the uniqueness of the irrigation regime, low evaporation, and the fact that water does not flow in vain. The most important thing is that in drip irrigation, the surface of the field soil does not harden because the water is delivered to the plant through pipes, as a result, there is no need to work between the rows.

When cotton is irrigated in the traditional way, i.e., through irrigation, part of the water is wasted in the bottom layers of the soil and part of it is wasted as a result of evaporation. Studies have shown that 1.5-2.0 thousand/cbm of water per hectare is wasted due to water evaporation and absorption. One of the urgent problems is the development and implementation of modern agrotechnical methods of irrigation of cotton and other cultivated crops in order to prevent negative situations. Irrigation technology by laying polyethylene film between cotton rows is a factor that reduces the demand for irrigation water and energy costs and increases soil fertility.

"TIAME" NRU Bukhara Institute of Natural Resources Management Educational and Scientific Center and in the fields of advanced farms of the Region, when watering by laying a black polyethylene film between the rows of cotton, water saving is on average 42 percent, it was observed that the additional cotton yield increased by 9.7-20.4 centners per hectare or by 23-43 percent. In non-traditional irrigation technology, plants have the ability to fully absorb nutrients as a result of uniform wetting of the soil, reduced evaporation of soil moisture after irrigation, mineral fertilizers are not washed away with water under pressure. Due to the death of weeds due to lack of sunlight, lack of compaction of the soil due to lack of cultivation between the rows, and due to the positive change of the chemical and water-physical properties of the fertile layer of the soil as a result of regular watering, due to the qualitative moistening of the soil of the root layer. it was determined that favorable conditions for the rapid development of the root system and the increase in productivity were created. Irrigation technology by laying black polyethylene film between rows of cotton is a technological direction that reduces the demand for irrigation water, reduces the costs of fuel, lubricants and equipment, and increases soil productivity.

15-20% water saving compared to conventional irrigation in case of irrigating cotton fields using portable flexible polyethylene pipes instead of ditches. It was observed that the land is

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evenly distributed and the useful crop area increases by 1.5-2.5%, and irrigation works are eased and manual labor is reduced up to 2 times. Modern portable flexible pipes provided to agriculture are adapted to 4 hectares of land, and 4 hectares of land are irrigated at the same time with the help of hoses. Due to the fact that the land area is irrigated in a short period of time, soil maturation occurs uniformly in all parts of the field. Portable flexible pipes are collected and re-installed before and after inter-row treatment. Due to the moderate and short-term supply of water to the field, the growth and development of cotton is positive, and the yield increases by 2.5-3.0 centners compared to the traditional irrigation method.

CONCLUSION

1. In the conditions of Bukhara region, water-saving irrigation technology is applied to the cotton crop in meadow swampy soils that have been irrigated for a long time (drip irrigation, black polyethylene film bed irrigation, portable flexible pipes) (irrigation) water-saving intensive technology has been shown to be an effective method. Along with a positive effect on the water physical properties of the soil, it has caused the plant to grow and develop at a high rate, as well as fuel and lubricant products, 50.0-56.0 percent saving of mineral fertilizer, labor and especially irrigation water was achieved.

2. Using water-saving irrigation technologies (drip irrigation, black polyethylene film bed irrigation, irrigation with the help of portable flexible pipes) in the irrigation of cotton, the productivity is from 3.0 to 20.4 centners per hectare. compared to the control variant, an additional yield was produced.

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